

USE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING LISTENING.

Dexqonova Madina

Fergana State University

Annotation: Any imagination when it comes to pedagogical creativity it is necessary to be able to distinguish constructed projects from real creativity. Because in practice that untested imaginary ideas sometimes cause great damage to pedagogical work. Pedagogical personnel in accordance with the requirements of the development of the educational system high professional training and ideological-political maturity, general issues of continuous growth of the level of culture are raised. The peoples of our country in educating their students ideologically and politically using important events, holidays and memorable dates in his life is important.

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Listening can be viewed as one of the most important skills that need to be acquired by learners in any language. It is one of the four skills that language learners acquire, and out of the four, it is one of the skills that are most frequently used by the individuals. Most instructors teach listening and speaking simultaneously. However, it is noted that beginners in any language, and specifically those that are considered to be non-literate, need to be exposed to more listening than speaking processes, again making listening a vital part of learning any language. Just as there are many methods a teacher can use to teach listening skills, there are many materials a teacher can use to instill these skills in their students. These materials fall into two main categories; authentic and unauthentic materials. The latter materials are also called scripted materials, given that they are edited and prepared specifically for the classroom. Controversy has arisen about the advantages and disadvantages of using authentic materials in teaching listening. There are those who argue that using original materials to teach listening is more beneficial for both students and teachers than using scripted materials. Each of these schools of thought has arguments it uses to support its arguments.

Authenticity in teaching contexts has been variously defined. Different definitions depend on the philosophical orientations of different scholars in the field. However, a common theme emerges among these definitions, a thread described by the central theme of these definitions. Martinez's definition is widely accepted in the field, and this is the definition adopted in this article. Martinez conceptualizes authenticity in linguistics as an authentic language form that comes from an authentic speaker or

writer, language directed at an authentic audience. Language is also designed or structured to convey a true message of some nature.

From this definition, it is easier to identify the actual material in teaching listening skills. According to Yingmai, authentic texts are written or spoken texts intended for native speakers of a particular language. This is, for example, a conversation in English. This conversation can only be understood by native English speakers, and the source of the conversation was directed at those speakers.

Thus, authentic texts are not specifically designed for language learners, and this is one of the factors that distinguish them from scripted texts. While scripted texts are intended for the specific consumption of language learners, authentic texts are intended for native speakers of that language. From the discussion above, for a text to be considered authentic, it must meet one basic criterion; it should not be designed specifically for language teaching purposes. For example, a radio interview between a celebrity and a host is aimed at English speakers, not for teaching English. However, this interview can be used to teach listening skills to a class of English learners.

Among the four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) that are recognized as the keys to 'knowing' the language, listening is probably the least important to be taught. Actually speaking and listening are always interrelated. However listening is the most "underdeveloped" skill. Basically, they realize that listening cannot be separated from other language skills like speaking, reading and writing. Listening is important since students may receive much of their information of their school through listening to instructors and to another. Listening has been regarded as the most frequently used language skills in the classroom. Furthermore nowadays listening skill is inclusive in national examination for the level of Senior High School. In Indonesia the teachers tend to ignore to teach this skill by skipping it even though it is clearly stated in curriculum. The teachers skip teaching listening for many reasons, such as lack of teaching material, lack of school facilities, the speakers in the recorded material speak too fast, the students do not understand the vocabularies and the sentences used by the speakers. The reason of lack of material for teaching of listening nowadays can be minimized, since the teachers can use authentic materials recorded from internet, TV and radio programs. Teachers can select the materials needed for their teaching based on the topic they are going to teach and the level of their students. Therefore teachers have no reasons to ignore and skip teaching of listening, for they can have their authentic teaching materials easily.

Modern effective methods of teaching listening skills everything ranging from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening ability is considered the ability

that can be learned best. Because to learn with a little more attention it was improved through simple and interesting activities and ultimately leads to good results. In this case, you are a junior or senior student. It doesn't matter if you work with groups, you follow to develop yourself if you use one of the methods. In front of senior students, first of all, previously learned oral speech the task is to preserve and strengthen their skills. In their speech It is necessary to participate in all the elements that they acquired during school students' speech should be more reliable and grounded.

Monologue speech approaches the natural form of speech, that is, an element of conversation is added as In this way, didogic speech and monologic speech are intermingled goes The content of oral speech becomes complicated. Based on the previous text from the conversation that interests and excites the students goes on to discuss. The quality of oral speech in the upper grades is oral. It is a qualitatively new stage in the acquisition of speech, which is creative from the text-language material forces to acquire new methods aimed at use.

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